

УДК:633.5(575.3)

FEATURES OF THE FORMATION AND DEVELOPMENT OF ENTREPRENEURSHIP IN THE REPUBLIC OF TAJIKISTAN

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Abstract. *This article presents the main areas of development and promotion of entrepreneurship in the Republic of Tajikistan, along with analysis and recommendations. It also notes that the development of entrepreneurship, particularly innovative entrepreneurship, is of great importance for replenishing and enriching local and state budgets. This process can lay the foundation for ensuring employment for citizens and, in this regard, for the achievement of one of the country's strategic goals, namely, rapid industrialization.*

Keywords: *entrepreneurship development, government regulation, innovative entrepreneurship, economic foundations, relationships, forms of entrepreneurship, investment development, taxation.*

Stages of the historical development of entrepreneurship in Tajikistan Despite the centuries-old path of formation and development of entrepreneurial relations, there is currently no generally accepted unified understanding of the essence and content of this most important economic institution - entrepreneurship. In this regard, there is a need for a retrospective analysis of the processes of the origin, formation and development of domestic entrepreneurship. Entrepreneurship in Tajikistan has a deep history and has existed in trade and crafts since ancient times. The evolution of entrepreneurship in Tajikistan can be divided into three historical periods, with some breakdown into internal sub-stages.

The first stage, the pre-Soviet period, covers the longest historical period from the birth of entrepreneurship in the East, the formation and development of the Great Silk Road to the fall of the Emirate of Bukhara. As you know, historically, the starting point of an entrepreneurial initiative was trading activity, when merchants, motivated by the difference in prices for goods, moved them from market to market, and small traders sold them in bazaars. The content of entrepreneurship was limited to using the difference in market prices, and the main feature was the degree of risk. Oriental bazaars served as a key form of mass retail trade organization. With the development of productive forces and commodity-money relations, branches of material production become the sphere of entrepreneurship. In these conditions, entrepreneurial success is determined not by the search for new markets, but by finding the most rational combination of applied factors of production based on entrepreneurial initiative.

The greatest development of entrepreneurship in Tajikistan dates back to the late 19th and early 20th centuries. At this time, the influx of Russian and foreign merchants to Turkestan and Bukhara increased dramatically. In order to make more profit, they invested their capital in the fuel and processing industries, the construction of railways and irrigation facilities. Trading firms, joint-stock companies and branches of large Russian banks were created, whose activities were mainly related to cotton operations. With the help of foreign capital and the revival of joint-stock activities, the construction of railways and various industrial facilities began, as well as the development of the foundations of the oil industry. There were 30 oil fields in the Turkestan Region, owned by private individuals and joint-stock companies. Since 1905, oil production near Kanibadam has been carried out by one of the largest partnerships - SANTO (Central Asian Oil Producing Partnership) with a fixed capital of 500 thousand rubles, which in 10 years exceeded two million rubles.

The second stage – the Soviet period of entrepreneurship development in Tajikistan covers the time period from the proclamation of the New Economic Policy to the beginning of perestroika. This period of Soviet rule in Tajikistan was characterized by the implementation of a policy aimed at

eliminating market relations, nationalizing all large enterprises, and expropriating the means of production and property of private entrepreneurs. Although it should be recognized that the years of the NEP (new economic policy), which lasted for a short time, brought some revival of entrepreneurship. In the 1930s, entrepreneurship was again curtailed, and only since the mid-80s, as a result of socio-political transformations called "perestroika," the decline of the Soviet system was marked by the revival of entrepreneurial activity.

The forms of entrepreneurial activity in the second half of the 80s of the twentieth century were: 9 centers of scientific and technical creativity of youth (NTTM); 9 temporary creative collectives (VTK); 9 individual entrepreneurship, the development of which originates from the USSR Law "On Individual Labor Activity", adopted in 1986. 9 cooperatives, when The cooperative movement has become widespread since the publication of the USSR Law "On Cooperation in the USSR" (1988). 9 private entrepreneurship (1989-1990) - its revival was due to the adoption of a number of regulatory documents on leasing; on the establishment of small and joint ventures. • The period of state sovereignty is associated with the revival and development of entrepreneurship in conditions of state independence and covers several internal stages: The 9th early stage (1991-1995), associated with the emergence of the legal foundations of entrepreneurship and the formation of its organizational and legal forms. Entrepreneurship under conditions of sovereignty began to develop actively in the early 90s, after the adoption on December 22, 1991 of the Laws "On Entrepreneurial Activity in the Republic of Tajikistan" (already at the beginning of 1992, the number of small enterprises exceeded 2.5 thousand, and the number of citizens engaged in entrepreneurial activity on the basis of patents without forming a legal entity amounted to 8.1 thousand. man) and "On privatization".

On June 20, 1993, Tajikistan's first business structure, the National Association of Small and Medium-Sized Businesses, was established to consolidate efforts and protect the rights of entrepreneurs.

The second was the stage of large-scale privatization and strengthening of the private sector (1996-2002).

The third stage is the formation of the foundations of a civilized system of state support for entrepreneurship and market infrastructure, as well as the deepening of reforms (2002- present). In recent years, as part of the reforms carried out in the country, regulatory legal acts have been improved, business registration and licensing procedures have been simplified, and a unified state electronic Register of Licensing Documents has been created, emphasizing the need to continue the continuity of the licensing system reform process, taking into account international experience. As a result of the improvement of the tax administration system, business entities have the opportunity to submit their declarations to the tax authorities in electronic form, which saves time and avoids unnecessary costs. Currently, about 8000 taxpayers in Tajikistan submit their declarations in this way. Another important component of the ongoing reforms is the simplification of customs procedures for export-import operations and transit of goods, in particular, the Customs Code was improved, a Single Stop and a Single Window system for processing export-import and transit operations were introduced.

The increasing importance of entrepreneurship in the transition economy and the high level of development of private entrepreneurship is a necessary component of the modern model of market-competitive management. Analyzing the state of Tajikistan's economy after independence, one can observe periods of recession, stagnation and economic stabilization, when private entrepreneurship is the most acceptable form of economic activity, which acquires its position in the market. In recent years, the contribution of the private sector to Tajikistan's economy has become increasingly visible. The share of this sector in the gross domestic product increased from 30% in 2002 to 60% in 2015. This indicator is very high in advanced economies, amounting to about 70%, which reflects the level of economic development and well-being of the population.

Tajikistan, which is undergoing deep market transformations due to the level of development of its industrial and economic potential and national identity, the consequences of fratricidal war and economic shock therapy, geographical location and national mentality, has to be in the position of

catching up and looking for its own path of development. This is compounded by the fact that it is impossible to fully utilize the experience of Western economic models and the examples of other former socialist countries that began transition processes a little earlier, due to different scales and starting conditions. Therefore, Tajikistan should form its own model of entrepreneurship development. In the study of the processes of formation and development of entrepreneurial activity in modern Tajikistan, it is impossible not to take into account some features. Currently, entrepreneurship is developing in the context of improving the legislative framework, increasing government activity to improve the investment climate, improve tax and customs policy, and improve foreign economic relations. At the same time, it should be noted that there are negative factors affecting the development of entrepreneurial activity, such as high bank loan rates, elements of corruption in government, tax and customs authorities, and poor development of market infrastructure elements. A distinctive feature of entrepreneurship in the republic continues to be the high proportion of the "shadow" sector. According to experts, it makes up from 30 to 40% of the real turnover of business entities, while a significant part of the resources used by "shadow" entrepreneurs turns out to be unused for solving national tasks. Currently, 0.38 accounts for every 1,000 inhabitants of the republic, including: in Sughd region – 0.29; in Khatlon region – 0.03; in districts of republican subordination – 0.18; in Dushanbe – 2.56 small enterprises. According to this indicator, the republic occupies one of the last places among the CIS countries.

The main trends in the development of marketing in Tajikistan at the present stage include:

- The movement away from the sales orientation towards the consumer orientation. An analysis of the marketing functions, the main number practiced by domestic enterprises, showed that sales support and promotion are considered the most important aspects of marketing activities, while the study of customer needs is given significantly less importance. At the same time, the development of consumer orientation as an important component of marketing orientation is beginning to emerge more clearly and become more significant.

Understanding the expediency of marketing orientation, which involves conducting marketing research of a strategic nature. In the practice of domestic companies, only one in seven uses marketing research to successfully adapt to the changing macro environment and develop a marketing strategy. At the same time, individual companies are trying to use marketing research to produce the initial data for strategic planning and strategic decision-making.

There has been a noticeable increase in the role of PR of leading companies, especially in the banking sector and in the field of information technology and services. We can say that the beginning of an improvement in the situation is obvious, but the high professional level of PR services is still far away.

Large-scale business development has not taken place in Tajikistan, as every third registered small enterprise in the country has suspended its activities due to difficulties and problems. Therefore, in the specific socio-economic conditions of the country, the quantitative growth potential of small businesses turned out to be significantly limited. Unfavorable trends in the development of small businesses are associated with both national social and economic problems, as well as with the peculiarities of small businesses. The liquidation of small enterprises is often the result of healthy economic competition, the inability of some entities to adapt to market changes, rebuild internal management, and establish effective relationships with consumers of products and services. Small business is crucial in transition economies, which, in fact, along with privatization, is the foundation on which the non-governmental sector of the economy and market economy institutions grow. Small business in Tajikistan provides:

- an increase in the number of owners, which means the formation of a middle class is the main guarantor of the irreversibility of reforms;
- the growth of citizens' incomes and, as a result, the smoothing of disparities in well-being;
- selection of the most energetic, capable individuals for whom small business becomes a school of self-realization;
- creation of new jobs;

- formation of necessary market skills and professional development;
- the introduction of new, often risky projects leading to technological and organizational innovations and the growth of modern knowledge-intensive industries and industries;
- Mobilization of material, financial and natural resources that would otherwise remain unclaimed, as well as their more efficient use;
- Improving the interconnection between different sectors of the economy, increasing their mobility and efficiency.

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